

	Main	Equals	Secondary
≥ avg	Green	Light Green	Very Light Green
(half, avg)	Yellow	Light Yellow	Very Light Yellow
min	Red	Light Red	Very Light Red

0 2 4 6 8 10 12 14 16 18 20
Total (out of 20)